

HJRS Link: [Journal of Academic Research for Humanities \(HEC-Recognized for 2022-2023\)](#)

Edition Link: [Journal of Academic Research for Humanities, 3\(1\) January-March 2023](#)

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Link of the Paper: <https://jar.bwo.org>

Historical Significance of Hutto Ram's Book Gulbahar in the Historiography of Baloch Tribes and Dera Ghazi Khan

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Paper Information

Citation of the paper:

(APA) Akhtar. Sohail, Shafique. Muhammad and Saddiqu. Muhammad (2023). Historical Significance of Hutto Ram's Book Gulbahar in the Historiography of Baloch Tribes and Dera Ghazi Khan. Journal of Academic Research for Humanities, 3(1), 1-7.

Subject Areas:

1 Literature
2 Historic Book Review

Timeline of the Paper:

Received on: 06-02-2023
Reviews Completed on: 28-03-2023
Accepted on: 13-04-2023
Online on: 25-04-2023

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Published by:

Abstract

Gulbahar is an important historical book about the history of Dera Ghazi Khan. It is considered the first book of the Urdu version of the History of Dera Ghazi Khan during the colonial era. Research in the context of any region and local history is always a difficult task due to the unavailability of historical documents. In the colonial rule in India with British historiography, the regional and local historians were also encouraged by the government to use the historical sense and promoted the historical work of the local writers. Among the different ingenious historians, Lala Hutto Ram is one of them. He was motivated by the British official of Dera Ghazi Khan to compile a book about the people of the district in light of the revenue record. On the demand of the British Deputy Commissioner, a book entitled Gulbahar was compiled by this Extra Assistant Commissioner, Hutto Ram, on the history of Dera Ghazi Khan. The book covers pre-colonial history, but mostly Dera Ghazi Khan and the colonial era. After Mr Bruce Notes on Dera Ghazi Khan The book contains a portion of some ancient history along with the major tribes and castes with their branches as the inhibiting in Dera Ghazi Khan. The book is also a comprehensive explanation of the socio-economic condition of the people of Dera Ghazi Khan. This work is a brief account of the book Gulbahar which provides useful information about this region Dera Ghazi Khan.

Keywords: Gulbahar, Hutto Ram, History, Dera Ghazi Khan, Castes, Revenue

Introduction

With the annexation of Punjab in 1849 after the 2nd Sikh War British forces occupied Dera Ghazi Khan. After the downfall of the Mughal dynasty in 1857 British controlled the region with new administrative Units i.e. Divisions and Districts. With other social changes, the pattern of history writing also changed. The British set a new pattern of historiography in India and focused on different identities of India to know about the socio-cultural norms of these identities. During British rule, enough work on historiography had been done by British Historians. The British diplomats, Officers, and soldiers also wrote their memories. The Bruce Notes on Dera Ghazi Khan, A Year on the Border of Punjab and Frontier, Account of the Kingdom of Kabul promoted a new trend of historiography in India. Among the remarkable historical work, some are considered very important. In this context of a new pattern of historiography, the historical work of Lala Hutto Ram entitled Gulbahar is the first major historical work on the regional history of Dera Ghazi Khan in Urdu version. He briefly wrote about the history of Dera Ghazi Khan.

In the past account, he explained the different phases of the history of this region. The first edition of this book had been published in 1862 by Qalat Publishers Quetta. In the book, Hutto Ram fulfilled their wish of Sandeman by describing the history and culture of the Baloch tribes and their customs and traditions beautifully, including the history of the region related to Balochistan. In the book, the blessings of the English government were also presented in the best way in many places so that people could see the good face of the English government. The author also describes the reforms and development during the English period.

Literature Review

It is an important historical source that has been republished once and its second edition is a great effort of Balochi Academy Quetta

that it was published after one hundred and twenty years.

The first part of the book is divided into four sub-parts which describe the history of the district along with the conditions of all the tehsils of Dera, Sanghar, Jampur, and Rajanpur and the conditions of towns and villages. While the geographical condition of the district and the surrounding states of Sindh, Bahawalpur, and Dera Ismail Khan, apart from Balochistan, the situation of the nations has been described. Detailed information has been provided on their population, religions, and customs. In the same section, the conditions of Hindus, Islam, and other peoples were described in detail. The author has discussed in detail the ancient families living in the district, the Pathans nations, the nations of Balochistan, and the history of Balochistan. In addition, valuable information on the nation, family, and state of Kalat.

In the second part of this book, Baloch Tuman Mazari, Laghari, Khosa, Gurchani, Darishak, Buzdar, Lo, and, Qaisrani, Khitran, Bugti, Murri, and other peoples have provided complete historical information on their customs, and traditions.

- The third part of the book includes the nation's business, employment, professions, and agricultural production.
- While the fourth part of the book is related to administrative matters, arrangement, etc.

Although Hutto Ram was the close companion, and colleague of Robert S, and man. He was the native Tehsil Rajanpur of District Dera Ghazi Khan. Hutto Ram is considered one of the important indigenous historians of the region, and he also wrote another important book Tareekh-e-Balochistan which confirms him as a good historian. Being an official he was advised by Robert S, and eman to write a book as information about the history of the region,

and he wrote this book in light of the revenue record of the District.

The study under review is a summary of Lala Haturam's book Gulbahar. In the book, Hutto Ram started the history of the new district of Dera Ghazi Khan from early Hindu history and completed it till the British era, and in it, he told us the names of the towns, cities, and regions as well as the party Tehsil Dera towards Dera Ghazi Khan. Ghazi Khan is the most important town besides Jampur and Rajanpur. He made them his topic of discussion. Tuman also mentioned the various tribes found within the district of Dera Ghazi Khan and the areas up to the hilly areas including the surrounding areas of Mira Ghazi Khan as well as Bahawalpur state. Khan, and the other tribes living along their territories, including Murri Bugti, and Khitran, have also given their place in this book. Dividing the Torah into books, and four main sections further divided into eighteen chapters. He spoke with fascination on the situation, and vents of the Hindus, the Muslims, and other nations, in the same, he wrote about other nations in the volume from Rajanpur to the present day, as well as Balochistan, and the history of Balochistan also discussed on the state. Hutto Ram also described the institutions of case justice administration, and the arrangement of I, and, and evils in the various four mobile districts settled within Dera Ghazi Khan.

Lala Hutto Ram's book "GulBahar" is a famous book of the time. This book, the described the geography of Dera Ghazi Khan; Cultural; Religious: National, and tribal history is written. Along with S, and eman Deputy Commissioner Dera Ghazi Khan, he visited the Koh Sulaiman. Heard from Elders; He kept penning notes of historical evidence, and avel observations. When these things were published in book form, people liked this unique work. Even the British Government of Punjab issued an order." On January 2, 1869, the Secretariat Government of Punjab

ordered that a book on Rajanpur, and District Dera Ghazi Khan should be compiled in English.

The introductory papers and correction papers are written in alphabetically numbered format In all ages, invading forces have been, and will continue to be mobilized to attack the "economy" or spread their ideas, and beliefs. Arabic also in the subcontinent; Persian; Mongolian; Pashtun; The Mughals, and the British have been attacking. The British also came here for the turmeric trade. They were aware of the political turmoil, and chaotic situation here. They started occupying the states of the subcontinent and even took control of the entire subcontinent. The most successful strategy is nationalism; Prejudices of regionalism, and sectarianism were to be raised. All kinds of debates took place during his time. He was very good at creating traitors by giving lures. Ministers would buy advisors or clan heads in return for privileges. When the local population started the independence movement, In the preface of Gul Bihar, Aziz Muhammad Bugti writes, "In this book, keeping in mind the same principle, every fight; the movement was defined as an sc and al which was carried out against the British Raj."

The British government used power, and modern weapons as well as politics; continued to strengthen its hold by underst, and in psychological, and regional issues. "The British government used to study the psychology, traditions, and customs of the people there, and respect them immensely while ruling each region.' When emperor Humayun became on the throne of the kingdom in Khorasan, he thought of attacking the subcontinent. He took 44 Baloch tribes with him under the leadership of Amir Chakar. (Amir Chakar later became famous as Mir Chakar). A large army went to Delhi. They got the victory. Many properties and estates were found. Mir Jalal Khan stayed at Satgraha near Sahiwal and died there. His tomb is also here.

Many Lashkari Balochs returned to Mount Sulaiman. Cattle rearing became their profession. Khosa settled in the mountains near Sakhi Sarwar. Now they are known as Khosa, Ch, and ia, Pitafi, and Sakhani. Sakhani was also a strong tribe in the past. In the western regions of the subcontinent, Arab; Persian; Baloch; Mughal; Said; Pathan; Abdali; Ghaznavi; Afghans, Lodhis, Sikhs, and British etc. have been invading with different intentions. They also benefited from the "booty" here, and propagated their religion. The natives here were hardworking, hardworking, and noble. They were agriculturists and a mal breeders. Their weapon was the sickle. They were hospitable, and peaceful people. The food crops were their own. They were rich. The clothes were their own. The skilled were their own, while the attackers had swords and organized groups. They ran everywhere. They were also called conquerors, and brave.

The Abbasid Caliphs also faced a downfall after ruling Baghdad for 535 years. They came to Sindh from Aleppo in 1068. Their number consisted of three thousand people. Mian Adam Abbasi was their leader. The head of the Sindh state was Mardam Abard. He warmly welcomed the Abbasids even to the point of partnership with the government. The time also came when Muhajir Abbasi also became the ruler. Mian Daud Abbasi became the government of Sarai. He was an experienced warrior. Soon his government was established from Kich Makran to Dera Ismail Khan and Kala Bagh. Millions of beggars also came under his rule. Many Baloches were included in his army who are still living in these areas. They spread their beliefs according to the conditions. He used to talk a lot. Along with the government, they also started taking Bait and continued the series of Peri-Muridi. When the situation in Sindh started to change, some of the Abbasids migrated to the east of the Indus River. He liked the I and s of Hakra River and Cholistan. He fought against the Hindus

living in the forts there and established a state in the entire region. He made Bahawalpur the capital. There are memories of him in the Dravidian fort.

In 1910 when the British founded the new model Dera Ghazi Khan. So the British government built the most modern palaces, and facilities for the nobles and influential people. From Faridabad Colony to Traffic Chaowk Gurchani Manzil; Mazari floor; inn floor; steep floor; Caesarean floor; Buzdar floor; Make Darishak Manzil and Khosa Manzil. Now the descendants of these chiefs have started selling that I, and s, and houses. He has been completing his education. This Mian Ghulam was an employee of Shah Abbasi Kalhoras. When he rebelled against the government, the Abbasids exiled him. His son Mir Bahr managed to gather an army. He fought a war to avenge his father and captured the Sindh government. But the Abbasids also remained active and killed Mir Bahr, and took over the government of Sindh.

In Sindh, the governments of the Abbasid Sarai Kalhors, and Talpurs are famous. Mir Shahdad Talpur, the chief of the Talpurs in the Dera Ghazi Khan district, settled here. This village and people are still present in large numbers on Bridge 14 from the peak to the south. S and eman was a CSP officer of the British government. He was promoted from AC, and appointed Deputy Commissioner of Dera Ghazi Khan district. He was a clever, tough, and ideological officer. He was posted here from 1866 to 1870. He understood the psychology of the Baloch. He met the head of each tribe, and he accepted their dem, and powers. Made friends with them, and made agreements with them. Made them part of the British government. These chieftains were made loyal to the British in return for concessions. If any group clashed, they were also given severe punishments with the support of these Balochs. They made separate Tumans in the areas of Rajanpur, and Dera Ghazi Khan. In each Tuman, The Chief of the

tribe was made as a Tumm and ar. He was granted the powers of an Honorary Magistrate to make him stronger. After controlling these areas, S, and eman, engaged the leading chiefs with him and left for Balochistan. S and man's goal is to survey the mountain within; It was to become familiar with the l, and routes, and to understand the psychology of the tribes. These chiefs were taken with them as tools and as personal guards. Horses for several months; He carefully examined the internal situation by travelling on mules, and foot.

In this journey, the important personalities of Mazari, Gurchani, Darishak, Leghari, Khosa, , and Lund etc. were taken along. Through them, they continued to invite, and spy on the chiefs there. Even today, some thinkers of Balochistan allege that the Baloch chiefs of Dera Ghazi Khan are responsible for the occupation of the British in the whole of Balochistan. Historian Aziz Mohammad Bugti writes in the expressive article of the book "Gul Bihar". Sir S, and Eman, the representative of the English government, established close personal relations with the chiefs of the Baloch tribes of Dera Ghazi Khan district, and through them arranged the English influence, and domination over Balochistan, in which he finally succeeded. Outwardly, this is called a small nation. it is a nation that performs the most important duty. They have literature, art, and poetry; There was a history and genealogy of the tribe. His recitation of the Rages increased the war craze. They systematically recalled the historical battles of the past. Services were also taken from them in times of happiness, and sorrow. He used to memorize tribal tales, poetic tales of bravery, and moments of grief. Each tribe had its own Dom. From them, Baloch tribes used to work. They were "real intellectuals". Who could change from wars, lost or won? Although they did not have a sword, but they had a "mighty tongue". Their job was to remember. Their

livelihood was the responsibility of the Sardar. Historical events and genealogies of many generations were being remembered from generation to generation. Babur became the first Mughal emperor of India in 1520. He died in 1540. His son Humayun ascended the throne. After the death of Humayun in 1556, Jalal-ud-Din Akbar got into the kingdom. During his time, Haji Khan Mirani Dudai Baloch came from Sindh to the north on the western bank of the river Indus. He became very familiar with this environment. Founded the village. Named it "Dera Ghazi Khan" after the name of his eldest son. Ghazi Khan's government was associated with Delhi and the Khorasan Kingdom. Ghazi Khan got the best advisers like Ganman Sachar Mahmud Gujar. He had dug canals and developed an agriculture system in the region. He planted trees along the canals. Put flowers in the garden. In those days, Bhagya was a common practice.

The powerful tribes used to attack the weaker tribes and take over their resources. Even in Ghazi Khan's state, Baloch, and non-Baloch, internal or external powers kept attacking. But the subordinate kings kept defending themselves. Mian Ghulam Shah Abbasi Kalhoras sent his servant Gudu Ram along with the soldiers. His associates Shafi Shah, Yar Shah, Musu Khan Nutkani, and Ganman Sachar were also arrested, and taken away. Ghazi Khan died in Hyderabad Sindh during his imprisonment and was buried there. The date of his death is 1188 Hijri recorded on his tomb. , and this section is also written on his grave in the Persian language. With these Sixteen descendants of Ghazi Khan, I ruled successively.

محروم رفت نیا زو خان غازی چو
مظلوم دست مر وطن یر مسافر
بشنو ست گفت وی تاریخ فرد
معصوم یار وی بشمر طفقغ

Lala Hutto Ram writes "Three routes lead from Sakhi Sarwar to Afghanistan and Iran.

The easy route. Goes from Rukni. This route is easy to carry grass for animals, and firewood for cooking, and cannons. The other route is the Musa Khel route which is a bit difficult. I used to go on foot. This path is straight but not suitable for carrying weapons.

In the canals of Dera Ghazi Khan, Ghazi Khan, and Mahmood Gujjar hag the canals under their supervision.

- **Sahiban Nala:** Sahib Khan Khakh was a government official. He dug under his supervision.
- **Nala Dhengana:** Its original name was Deha Gana, which became famous. It was dug by Badruddin Mimar, a government employee.
- **Nala Fazal Waha:** Tam, and ar Fazal Ali Khan Lind were excavated in 1861.
- **Nala Manka:** Excavated in 1863 at the request of Jamal Leghari.
- **Nala Kasturi:** Ghazi Khan bought one lakh rupees' worth of musk from a Hindu merchant, and poured it into Dera Nahar. The smell spread for several days. Later, this channel became famous. There is a vast fertile plain to the west of the Indus River and the east of Mount Sulaiman. Agricultural professionals and cattle herders lived here. These people were not organized in the form of tribes. While the mountain Baloch were also organized, and equipped with modern weapons. Their profession was robbery, robbery, and wealth-raising. They were warriors.

Their battles were fought every day, and Lala Hutto Rram told about the different battles as follows;

Chakar Rind and Goharam Lashari's quarrel was over a wedding ceremony at a horse race. The winner was killed instead of being rewarded. Such a battle ensued that hundreds of people were killed on both sides.

- Battle of Mazari, and Lunds
- Battle of Ch, and is, and Mazaris
- Jakhrani , and Mazari dispute
- Bugti , and Mazari quarrel

- Jaskani, and Darishka quarrel
- Battle of Lagaris , and Khosas

After many years of rivalry, they reconciled. As a guarantee, it was decided that 30 families should be settled next to each other. Therefore, 30 families were settled in Taman Laghari Basti Mamori, and 30 families were settled in Bela Taman Khosa. Earlier, there was a war between the tribes with arrows and swords. Now the war of politics is through votes. The objectives were economic before, and are still economic.

Rituals:

It is customary to give "Hal" to the Baloch people. There was no education so people used to listen, and traveled to increase their knowledge. There was an exchange of information. There was awareness of the geography and the area. Baloch is a brave, and warrior nation, so for the legacy of bravery, the child would be drowned by swinging a sword in water. That would have been heroic nonsense.

Baloch es are mention in Shahnama as a nation of brave , and rebellious people who are devoted to Karbala. They consider Mullah Imam Hussain (as) as their leader , and hero.

بادشاه خدمت خیر آمد
سپاه بلوچی از زمین کشته که
کشید جفا تیغ حسینان بر که آندم
برید نبی قلب گفته الامین روح
مسکینی زغیب ہاتف گفت
دینی ے برید را سردین

In short, the book Gulbahar of Hutto Ram is a brief history of Dera Ghazi Khan with ethnic composition, socio-cultural condition of the people, revenue collection, the tribes, and the castes of the region, small, and big towns, villages, agriculture, norms, and traditions, Urs, fairs, Sufis, and Shrine, and the administrative position of the Dera Ghazi Khan.

Conclusion

The above discussion deals with the book Gulbahar which is a brief account of

information about District Dera Ghazi Khan. Lala Haturam is seen as the pioneer historian of regional history, especially in the historiography of the Baloch tribes, and Dera Ghazi Khan. His book Gulbahar is regarded as the primary source on the history of Dera Ghazi Khan. Apart from this, the author also wrote about the history of Balochistan, but it will be about Gulbahar. Gulbahar is a detailed book. However, if the soundness of the book is to be talked about, the author Lala Hutto Ram has quoted a lot of information, many of which need to be examined in the manner of historical criticism. Because there are no references in this book which is merely covered in the light of Revenue Record or Dena Gazette. But despite this, the book is rich in information, and due to the unavailability of primary sources, it is itself an important historical source. In which the author has tried his best to provide information in his way. However, even if the book is declared as an early historical achievement, it will not be out of place because it is an effort of that time when the lack of motivation to adopt the modern prevailing principles of historiography as a professional historian was noticeable, and the historian, not being regular, stayed away from the art of adapting the historical, and research efforts in a critical mood, which is not a deliberate mistake.

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